

Vegetation Structure of Western Himalayan Temperate Forests in Ghamot National Park in Neelum Valley Azad Jammu And Kashmir, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

The Himalayan forest ecosystem offers important services and income to distant mountain communities. The current study was conducted to assess the vegetation structure of Ghamot National Park in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. A total of 20 locales were chosen, 452 quadrates were laid in 20 localities, and 489 plant species from 77 families were recorded in 18 sites with 18 communities. 9 (1.84%) of the 489 species were trees, 32 (6.54%) were shrubs, and 448 (91.61%) were herbaceous, including 46 fern species. Asteraceae (n=46, 9%) had the most species in the research region, followed by Poaceae (32, 7%), Ranunculaceae (n=29, 6%), Lammiaceae (n=25, 5%), Rosaceae (n=22, 4%), and Fabaceae (21, 4%). Out of the entire number of families (n=77), dominating families (n=16, 20.77) account for 63% of the local flora, with 308 species, while remaining families (n=61, 79.22) account for 37% of the whole flora, with 1-7 species. The importance value index (IVI) of each community's documented species was determined. *Juniperus communis* had the highest average IVI (4.99), followed by *Abies pindrow* (4.40), *Salix flabellaris* (3.70), *Viburnum grandiflorum* (3.65), and *Betula utilis* (3.65). To protect and maintain forest services, authorities should establish conservation policies at the local and regional levels.

Keywords: Conservation, Biodiversity, Dominant, Forest, Families, Elevation, Communities, Himalayan Mountains

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INTRODUCTION

The Himalayas are home to an estimated 25,000 plant species, accounting for 10% of the world's total, with 21 vegetation types and 60 Eco region types (Helmer et al., 2002). The most essential components of regional hotspot biodiversity have been studied: the species composition and vegetative structure of Himalayan forest types. The alpine zone is a major reservoir of biodiversity, with many rare and endangered species (Korner, 2003). The alpine and sub-alpine zones of the Western Himalayas (WH) are far more geographically extensive than those of the Eastern Himalayas (EH), as demonstrated by a larger pool of vascular plants (Rawat, 2007).

Forest ecosystems provide valuable services such as air quality regulation, waste treatment, water purification, and water flow regulation (Hein et al., 2006); soil erosion prevention, climate regulation, and soil fertility maintenance (Klein et al., 2007); pollination, seed dispersal, pest and disease regulation (Gallai et al., 2009); and preservation of migratory species life cycles, nutrient recycling, spiritual, religious, and aesthetic values, cultural diversity, and biodiversity (De Groot et al., 2002). Approximately 10% of the world's population is directly dependent on mountain forest resources, with an additional 40% relying on them indirectly (Schild, 2016).

Sustainable forest structure management is crucial for local populations' survival as well as the present climatic conditions (Cronin & Pandya, 2009). More than 60% of the Himalayan forest ecosystem was lost during the preceding century (Pokhriyal et al., 2010). Poor economic conditions, population growth, and a lack of information among local populations about forest surrounding regions pose the biggest threats to forest diversity (Gairola et al., 2008). Deforestation, overgrazing, trampling, soil erosion, overexploitation, overuse, and incorrect collection all put enormous biotic strain on local forests, negatively impacting forest structure and functions (Costanza et al., 1997).

Because of the fragility and remoteness of the Himalayan Mountains, data on vegetation dynamics in Kashmir valley are limited. A survey of the literature finds that prior work in AJK has been confined and restricted to small regions, particularly at higher elevations, due to remoteness, inaccessibility, and insecurity caused by continuing military activity between Pakistan and India along the Line of Control (Dad & Khan, 2011; Altaf, and Umair. 2022).

Existing knowledge gaps underlined the need for a deeper understanding of western Himalayan vegetation dynamics in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, resulting in the current study's concept and approach. The present research Endeavour was designed to uncover new ecological routes and map the whole flora of Ghamot National Park. The study was conducted in an altitudinal range of 2300m-4400m, in a variety of locations and habitats with varying viewpoints and terrain. This study examined vegetation at diverse altitudinal gradients, different perspectives, altering slope degrees, and unique ecosystems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Ghamot National Park (GNP) is located in the upper Neelum valley, a section of the eastern Himalayas, 170 kilometers north of Muzaffarabad, the capital of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The research region is located at latitude 35° 24 N and longitude 73° 57 E, at an elevation of 2439-4949 m above sea level. The park is located on the outskirts of Surgan Nullah, approximately 25 kilometers from Sharda. The Kaghan Valley in NWFP borders it on the west, while Indian-occupied Jammu and Kashmir borders it on the east. The road from Sharda to Ghamot National Park is seven kilometers long and consists of a carpeted road up to Surgan, a small town at the entrance to the Surgan-valley, and a further 16 to 18 kilometers of Jeep-able roads

from Surgan village to Ghamot village, a small settlement at the park's boundary. The climate varies with altitude, but the forest regions in the research area are commonly classified as moist temperate forest, dry temperate forest, sub-alpine scrub, and alpine meadows. Winters are quite cold, with thick snowfall. Summers are quite nice and refreshing. Snow on high summits may last until June or even later (glacier) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location map of study area

Floristic Diversity analysis

Following Ahmed and Shaukat, (2012) 14 phytosociology vegetation sample surveys were done in July, August, September, and November of 2020 and February to June of 2021. For vegetation sampling, a line transect with multiple quadrat approach was utilised. In 20 places, 85 line transects (total area covered 24km) with 425 quadrates were set. The length of the transect varied depending on topography and vegetation factors, but the maximum length was 500m and the lowest length was 250m. Along the transect line, quadrates were placed. All of the quadrates placed were of uniform size and quantity, with the maximum number of quadrates for shrubs in each locale being 15, 10 for shrubs, and 5 for trees. Dimensions of each quadrat were 1x1m², 5x5m² and 10x10m² for herbs, shrubs and trees respectively (Figure 2).

Phytosociological analysis

Following Hamayun shaheen et al. (2017), standard phytosociological methods were employed to assess density, frequency, canopy cover, relative values, and the important value index. To calculate the diversity indices, Simpson (1949) and Shannon and Weaver (1979) were employed (1959). Pielou (1964) computed evenness, whereas Menhinick (1964) measured species richness (1975). Community maturity was assessed after Pichi-Sermolli (1948) (Shaheen et al., 2015).

Local conservation status assessment

An average IVI was calculated for each species to determine representation of species in community. Following Hamayun shaheen et al. (2017) local status was determined on the basis of average IVI values of species, average IVI was classified into five conservation classes i.e. class abundant "A" = average IVI ≥ 2 , class common "C" =

average $IVI < 2$ and ≥ 0.50 , class fairly common “FC”= average $IVI < 0.50$ and ≥ 0.3 , Class becoming rare “BR”= average $IVI < 0.3$ and ≥ 0.1 and class rare “R”= average $IVI < 0.1$.

Figure 2: Line transect survey for phytosociology attributes collection, herbs quadrates (a), slope measurement (b), shrubs quadrates (c) and trees quadrates (d).

RESULTS

A total of 20 localities were chosen, 452 quadrates were laid in 20 localities, and 489 plant species from 77 families were recorded in 18 sites with 18 communities. 9 (1.84%) of the 489 species were trees, 32 (6.54%) were shrubs, and 448 (91.61%) were herbaceous, including 46 fern species (Table 1).

Recorded dominant families in study area with maximum number of species were Asteraceae (n=46, 9%) followed by Poaceae (32, 7%), Ranunculaceae, (n=29, 6%), Lammiaceae (n=25, 5%), Rosaceae (n=22, 4%) and Fabaceae (21, 4%) respectively. Other families including Dryopteridaceae (n=18, 4%), Apiaceae, (n=16, 3%), Bracicaceae (n=12, 2%), Scrophularaceae (n=12, 2%), Boraginaceae (n=12, 2%), Primulaceae (n=14, 3%), Gentianaceae (n=10, 2%) Caryophyllaceae (n=9, 2%) and Saxifragaceae (n= 8, 2%) also have significant contribution in floristic composition of study area (Figure 3).

Phyto-sociological Attributes of Communities

A total of 18 communities were recorded, with 9 communities recorded at elevations ranging from 2400m to 3500m and the remaining 9 communities recorded at elevations ranging from 3500m to 4250m. For each species in each community, phytosociological primary attributes such as density, frequency, and cover were recorded, and these values were used to calculate IVI for each species in each community.

Figure 3. Families’ contribution in floristic composition in study area

Key: class abundant “A” = average IVI ≥ 2 , class common “C” = average IVI < 2 and ≥ 0.50 , class fairly common “FC” = average IVI < 0.50 and ≥ 0.3 , Class becoming rare “BR” = average IVI < 0.3 and ≥ 0.1 and class rare “R” = average IVI < 0.1 .

The communities were named after three dominant species in each community (4.13) for structure and formation analysis of vegetation communities importance value index (IVI) of all the recorded species in each community was calculated. *Juniperus communis* had the highest IVI (4.99), followed by *Abies pindrow* (4.40), *Salix flabellaris* (3.70), *Viburnum grandiflorum* (3.65), and *Betula utilis* (3.65). (3.39). *Picea Wallichiana* (2.68), *Eremopoa altaica* (2.46), *Poa nemoralis* (2.45), *Bistorta affinis* (2.39), *Rhododendron campanulatum* (2.38), *Juncus membranaceus* (2.34), *Bistorta amplexicaulis* (2.32), *Geranium pratense* (2.25), *Rosa webbiana* (2.21) (Figure 4).

To evaluate the differences between different observed communities, the Shannon Wiener index for overall diversity pattern of specific site and Simpson index for species dominance pattern were calculated. Shannon diversity had a maximum value (4.53) at the Kothalii site for community C10 (*Rosa-Gaultheria-Aconitum*), and

a minimum value (3.07) at the Ghol basti top site for community C13 (Sibbaldia-Bistorta-Lagotis). Simpson had the highest value (0.98) for community C10 (Rosa-Gaultheria-Aconitum) at Ghol basti and the lowest value (0.81) for C2 (Abies-Viburnum-Juniperus) at Saral site. Evenness and Menhinick richness indexes were calculated from primary phytosociological data to determine the distribution pattern of species and diversity in a community. The maximum value (0.92, 1.92) of richness and evenness was recorded at site Jor Di Gali for C17 (Anaphalis-Rheum-Poa) and site Kothalii for C10 (Rosa-Gaultheria-Aconitum), respectively, while the minimum values (0.81, 0.99) were recorded at site Saral for community C2 (Abies-Viburnum-Juniperus) and site Top of Alihol Baik for. A community maturity index was calculated to indicate the climax and regular disturbance in a community. The highest maturity index (82.9%) was recorded at site Ghamot village for community C1 (Pinus - Indigofera-Viburnum), while the lowest value of maturity index was recorded at site Samgam Mali for community C5 (Rosa-Abies-Betula) (Table 2).

Figure 4: Recorded average IVI of dominant plant species in communities in study area.

Figure 5: Plant diversity *Aconitum heterophyllum* (A), *Betula utilis* (B), *Vibernum grandiflorum* (C), *Bergenia ciliate* (D) in study area during 2020-21

DISCUSSION

Current floristic baseline studies confirm the presence of 489 plant species from 77 families, including trees (n=9; 1.84%), shrubs (n=32, 6.54%), and herbs (n= 448, 91.61%). Asteraceae (n=46, 9%), Poaceae (n=32, 7%), and Ranunculaceae (n=29, 6%) were the dominant plant families with the most species, accounting for 37% of the local flora of the study area. Neelum Valley is rich in natural resources and represents phytogeographic features of the Sino Himalayan region (Qamar et al., 2010). Moist temperate forest, dry temperate forest, subalpine scrub, and alpine pastures are all found in the study area (Qamar et al., 2012) The area experiences long and harsh winters from mid-December to the end of April, followed by a very short mild summer from mid-June to September These physiographic and climatic features provide a high level of ecosystem diversity, supporting a diverse range of vegetation (Shaheen et al., 2017). Qamar et al. (2010) reported 7 species of gymnosperms, 404 species of angiosperms, 46 species of grasses, 33 species of ferns, and 14 species of fungi in their ethno botanical study of wild medicinal plants of Neelum valley. According to Mir et al., (2017) and Bano et al., (2013), the flora of Azad Jammu and Kashmir's Western Himalayan High Lands consists of 517 plant species divided into 78 families and 239 genera. Plant families such as Roaceae, Asteraceae, Lamiaceae, Poaceae, and Fabaceae are the most numerous and diverse in the western Himalayas. In addition, Chawla et al. (2008) reported that the presence of herbaceous families in the western Himalaya may be indicative of a high alpine environment. These indicator families are adapted to a variety of stresses at high altitudes, and some species are even restricted to the harsh conditions of the alpine zone in all regions of the world (Scherrer et al., 2011; Gottfried et al., 2012). Because members of these families have a broad ecological range and a distinct growth pattern, these families are abundant (Klimes and Dolezal, 2010; Korner et al., 2011). Ullah et al. (2015) described 86 plant species from Azad Jammu and Kashmir's western Himalayan region, including Cyperaceae, Poaceae, and Juncaceae. In total, 18 plant communities were studied in the study area. Phytosociological characteristics revealed the dominance of a few representative plant species based on their average importance value index, which included *Betula utilis*, *Salix flabellaris*, *Juncus membranaceous*, *Abies pindrow*, *Pinus wallichiana*, *Vibernum grandiflorum*, and *Rhododendron campanulatum* were among the species studied. Shaheen et al. (2017) discovered a similar species in Neelum

Valley. These dominant species are structurally significant and serve as indicators of Himalaya Highland vegetation (Cochaard and Dar, 2014; Shaheen et al., 2017).

A number of phytosociological studies on high mountains in various parts of the world supported the current study by demonstrating that the highest importance value percentages were recorded for similar taxa in the Himalayas of India, Pakistan, and Nepal (Sharma et al., 2014; Negi et al., 2014; Shaheen et al., 2017; Mir et al., 2017). Plant life on the high ground, according to Dolezal and Strutek (2002), showed variations in vegetation structure, diversity, and life forms that are directly related to ecological factors and human activities. The species composition of communities recorded in similar environmental conditions was similar due to similar habitat conditions in terms of nutrients and climate (Khan et al., 2016). According to Pauli et al. (2007), the allocation pattern of plant species within the alpine and sub-alpine regions is primarily influenced by climate or climate-influenced environmental factors. The local conservation status of plant species was classified using the average importance value index (IVI). According to Pujol et al. (2006) and Shaheen et al. (2017), phytosociological attribute studies based on IVI values provide an excellent understanding of plant species distribution and conservation status. Some trees (*Prunus cornuta*, *Acer cappadocium*, and *Acer caesium*), shrubs (*Cassiope fastigiata*, *Lonicera myrtillus*, *Juniperus excels*), and herb species in the study area had low average IVI values and are considered rare in the area. Shaheen et al. (2017) found a similar species with a low IVI in western Himalaya. The decrease in plant diversity in the study area could be attributed to habitat modification, encroachment, climate change, deforestation, and over-exploitation of natural resources such as forager collection and timber extraction. Human population growth is outpacing land holding, posing serious threats to hunger and land ownership. As a result, humans attempt to expand their range into adjacent undisturbed lands (IUCN, 2006). This study's phytosociology results and proposed management prescriptions may assist the state government in planning conservation strategies for the study area.

CONCLUSION

The current study aids in the better understanding of floral diversity in Western Himalayan ecosystems, specifically species composition, community structure, and diversity. The current study recorded a total of 658 plant species (457) in the study area along elevation gradients with varying topographic features. Ghamot National Park (study area) supports a large number of plants species, including globally threatened and rare species, according to the study. The current study is the first to look at the baseline flora of Ghamot National Park. This study will be informative and valuable to state departments for effective conservation planning, ecological research studies, and the development of a management plan for a national park.

Conflict of interest

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

Ethics approval

No approval of research ethics committees was required to accomplish the goals of this study because experimental work was conducted with an unregulated species.

Consent to participate: Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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Table 1: Check list of plant species reported in study area.

Sr.	Families	Species (scientific name)	Vernacular name	Habit	Average IVI	Local status
1	Acanthaceae	<i>Acer caesium</i>	Tarkanna	T(Tree)	1.47	C
2	Betulaceae	<i>Betula utilis</i>	Bhurj pattra	T	3.39	A
3	Hippocastanaceae	<i>Aesculus indica</i>	Bankhor	T	0.24	FC
4	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus cornuta</i>	Chhery	T	0.19	FC
		<i>Prunus padus</i>	--	T	0.43	FC
5	Pinaceae	<i>Piceae wallichiana</i>	Kail, Bluepine	T	2.68	A
		<i>Piceae smithiana</i>	Kachhal, spruce	T	1.48	C
		<i>Abies pindrow</i>	Silver fir	T	4.40	A
6	Taxaceae	<i>Taxus wallichiana</i>	Barmi, yew	T	0.41	C
7	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Lonicera asperifolia</i>	Loorni	S (Shrub)	0.66	C
8		<i>Lonicera hispidia</i>	Phoot	S	0.28	C
		<i>Lonicera myrtillus</i>	Phoot	S	0.50	FC
		<i>Lonicera webbiana</i>	Bhdy Katri	S	2.21	A
09	Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera gerardiana</i>	Kainthi	S	0.52	C
10	Rosaceae	<i>Potentilla nepalensis</i>	----	S	0.07	BR
		<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	Black berry	S	2.00	A
		<i>Spiraea arcuata</i>		S	0.09	BR
11	Rutaceae	<i>Skimmia laureola</i>	Nera	S	0.17	FC
12	Caprifoliaceae	<i>Viburnum cotinifolium</i>		S	0.55	C
		<i>Viburnum grandiflorum</i>	Guch	S	3.65	A
		<i>Viburnum nervosum</i>	-	S	2.09	A
13	Cupressaceae.	<i>Juniperus communis</i>	Bhenti	S	4.99	A
14	Ephedraceae	<i>Ephedra gerardiana</i>	Bhenti	S	0.52	FC
15	Berberidaceae	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	Sumblu	S	0.24	FC
		<i>Berberis jaeschkeana</i>	Kala Sumbal	S	1.12	C
		<i>Berberis aitchisonii Ahrendt</i>	Sumbl	S	0.45	FC
16	Rosaceae	<i>Cotoneaster affinis</i>	Loonri	S	0.21	FC
		<i>Cotoneaster bacillaris</i>	Loonri	S	0.20	C
17	Ericaceae	<i>Gaultheria trichophylla</i>	Ferozi Boti	S	0.57	FC
		<i>Rhododendron anthopogon</i>	Nichnee	S	0.12	FC
		<i>Rhododendron arbortium Smith</i>	Nichnee	S	0.26	FC
		<i>Rhododendron campanulatum</i>	Nichnee	S	2.38	A
18	Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera himalayensis Ali</i>	Kenthee	S	0.32	FC
19	Hamamelidaceae	<i>Parrotiopsis jacquemontiana</i>	Peshor	S	0.23	FC
20	Grossulariaceae	<i>Ribes himalense.</i>		S	0.33	BR
21	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa alpina L.</i>	Mali Phol	S	0.67	C
		<i>Rosa webbiana</i>		S	2.21	A
		<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	Jangli Gulab	S	2.00	A
		<i>Rubus ulmifolius</i>	Gangli Meva	S	0.11	FC
		<i>Rosa alpina</i>	Kun Chari	S	0.67	C
22	Salicaceae	<i>Salix flabellaris</i>		S	3.70	A
23	Woodsiaceae	<i>Woodsia alpina.</i>		F(Fern)	0.31	FC
		<i>Athyrium filix-femina</i>		F	0.21	BR
		<i>Athyrium imbricatum.</i>		F	0.14	BR
		<i>Athyrium wallichianum</i>		F	0.10	BR
		<i>Gymnocarpium dryopteris</i>		F	0.15	BR
24	Dryopteridaceae	<i>Polystichum attenuatum</i>		F	0.35	BR
		<i>Polystichum bakerianum</i>		F	0.32	BR
		<i>Polystichum castaneum</i>		F	0.34	BR
		<i>Polystichum lachenense</i>		F	0.21	BR
		<i>Polystichum lonchitis</i>		F	0.12	BR
		<i>Polystichum prescottianum</i>		F	0.13	BR
		<i>Polystichum yunnanense</i>	Kakwa	F	0.19	BR
		<i>Dryopteris barbigera</i>		F	0.39	FC
		<i>Dryopteris blanfordii</i>		F	0.48	FC
		<i>Dryopteris blanfordii</i>		F	0.28	BR
		<i>Dryopteris juxtaposita</i>		F	0.23	BR
		<i>Dryopteris ramosa</i>		F	0.18	BR
		<i>Dryopteris redactopinnata</i>		F	0.10	BR
		<i>Dryopteris stewartii</i>		F	0.62	FC
		<i>Dryopteris wallichiana (</i>		F	0.16	BR
		<i>Dryopteris filix-mas</i>	Langroo	F	0.16	BR
		<i>Dryopteris marginata</i>	Langroo	F	0.21	BR
		<i>Dryopteris thelypteris</i>	Langroo	F	0.11	BR
25	Adiantaceae	<i>Adiantum capillus.</i>	Kakwa	F	0.32	FC
		<i>Adiantum pedatum.</i>	Kakwa	F	0.36	FC
		<i>Adiantum trichomanes</i>	Kakwa	F	0.60	FC
		<i>Adiantum caudatum</i>	Kakwa	F	0.20	BR
		<i>Adiantum venustum</i>	Kakwa	F	0.41	FC
		<i>Cryptogramma brunomiana</i>		F	0.41	FC
26	Aspleniaceae	<i>Asplenium adiantum-nigrum</i>		F	0.28	BR
		<i>Asplenium fontanum</i>		F	0.14	FC
		<i>Asplenium septentrional</i>		F	0.10	BR
		<i>Asplenium trichomanes L.</i>		F	0.34	FC
27	Ophioglossaceae	<i>Botrychium matricarifoliu</i>		F	0.16	BR
28	Aspleniaceae	<i>Ceterach officinarum Willd.</i>		F	0.13	BR
29	Peridaceae	<i>Cheilanthes persica</i>		F	0.23	BR
		<i>Cryptogramma stelleri</i>		F	0.11	BR
		<i>Onychium contiguum</i>		F	0.8	FC
		<i>Pellaea nitidula</i>		F	0.11	BR
		<i>Onychium japonicum</i>		F	0.19	BR
30	Cystopteridaceae	<i>Cystopteris dickieana</i>		F	0.14	BR
		<i>Cystopteris fragilis</i>		F	0.12	BR
		<i>Cystopteris montana</i>		F	0.21	BR
31	Osmundaceae	<i>Osmunda claytoniana</i>		F	0.18	BR
		<i>Osmunda regalis</i>		F	0.08	BR

32	Nephrolepidaceae	<i>Nephrolepis cordifolia</i>		Fern	0.83	FC		
33	Asteraceae	<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	Sultani Boti	H(Herb)	0.12	BR		
		<i>Ainsliaea aptera</i>		H	0.34	FC		
		<i>Ainsliaea latifolia</i>		H	0.11	BR		
		<i>Allardia tomentosa Decne.</i>		H	0.45	FC		
		<i>Anaphalis boissieri Grgiadou</i>	Kali Boti	H	1.32	FC		
		<i>Anaphalis nepalensis</i>	Peli Boti	H	0.78	FC		
		<i>Anaphalis triplinervis</i>	Chiti Boti	H	0.98	FC		
		<i>Artemisia absinthium</i>	Jahoo	H	0.34	FC		
		<i>Artemisia annua</i>	Jahoo	H	0.33	FC		
		<i>Artemisia herba-alba</i>	Jahoo	H	0.04	R		
		<i>Artemisia japonica Thunb.</i>	Chita Jahoo	H	0.46	FC		
		<i>Artemisia maritima</i>	Sur Ganda	H	0.65	FC		
		<i>Carduus edelbergii</i>		H	0.89	FC		
		<i>Aster alpinus</i>		H	0.34	FC		
		<i>Carduus nutans.</i>	Kanda	H	0.12	BR		
		<i>Aster falconeri</i>		H	1.53	C		
		<i>Aster himalaicus</i>		H	0.87	FC		
		<i>Gnaphalium hypoleucum</i>		H	0.43	FC		
		<i>Gnephallium affine</i>		H	0.22	BR		
		<i>Jurania macrocephala</i>	Jugal Dhop	H	0.05	R		
		<i>Inula grandiflora Willd</i>		H	0.36	FC		
		<i>Inula orientalis Lam.</i>		H	0.89	FC		
		<i>Inula royleana</i>		H	0.04	BR		
		<i>Inula hookeri</i>		H	0.87	FC		
		<i>Inula spiraeifolia</i>		H	0.36	FC		
		<i>Lentopodium himalayanaum</i>		H	0.45	FC		
		<i>Leontopodium leontopodium</i>		H	0.48	FC		
		<i>Leontopodium alpinum</i>		H	0.29	BR		
		<i>Leontopodium jacotianum Beauverd</i>		H	0.45	FC		
		<i>Ligularia amplexicaulia</i>		H	0.20	BR		
		<i>Ligularia fischeri</i>		H	0.87	FC		
		<i>Psychrogeton andryaloides</i>		H	1.02	C		
		<i>Saussurea albescens Sch.Bip</i>		H	0.02	R		
		<i>Saussurea alpina</i>	Kori Jari	H	0.98	FC		
		<i>Saussurea costus</i>	Kuth	H	0.17	BR		
		<i>Saussurea fastuosa</i>	Kuth	H	0.02	R		
		<i>Saussurea candicans</i>	Richh Kuth	H	0.08	R		
		<i>Senecio chrysanthemoides</i>	Bagoo	H	0.36	FC		
		<i>Senecio graciliflorus</i>	Bagoo	H	2.48	A		
		<i>Senecio jacquemontianus</i>		H	0.04	R		
		<i>Solidago virga-aurea</i>	Muta Kesh	H	0.32	FC		
		<i>Sonchus asper</i>		H	0.45	FC		
		<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	Kundiari	H	0.98	FC		
		<i>Tanacetum dolichophyllum Kitam</i>	Mali ki Jahoo	H	0.89	FC		
		<i>Taraxacum tibetanum</i>	Mali ki Hand	H	0.78	FC		
		<i>Taraxacum laevigatum</i>	Hand	H	0.43	FC		
		<i>Taraxacum obovatum</i>	Hand	H	0.14	BR		
<i>Taraxecum officinale</i>	Hand	H	0.05	R				
<i>Tussilago farfara.</i>		H	0.80	FC				
34	Ranunculaceae	<i>Aconitum ferox Wallich ex Seringe</i>	Patrees	H	0.05	R		
		<i>Aconitum heterophyllum</i>	Patrees	H	0.06	R		
		<i>Aconitum laeve</i>	Patrees	H	0.46	FC		
		<i>Aconitum violaceum</i>	Mohri	H	0.14	FC		
		<i>Aconitum chyasmenthium</i>	Mohri	H	0.33	FC		
		<i>Actaea spicata</i>	Muniri	H	0.99	FC		
		<i>Anemone obtusiloba</i>		H	0.12	BR		
		<i>Anemone rupicola Cambess.</i>		H	1.05	C		
		<i>Anemone tetrasepala</i>		H	0.12	BR		
		<i>Anemone rivularis</i>		H	0.78	FC		
		<i>Aquilegia fragrans Benth.</i>	Phkli Jar	H	0.33	FC		
		<i>Aquilegia nivalis</i>	Phkli Jar	H	0.87	FC		
		<i>Aquilegia pubiflora</i>	Phkli Jar	H	0.69	FC		
		<i>Caltha alba</i>	Kakari Patra	H	0.06	R		
		<i>Delphinium denudatum</i>		H	0.34	FC		
		<i>Delphinium roylei Munz.</i>		H	0.84	FC		
		<i>Delphinium vestitum</i>		H	0.98	FC		
		<i>Delphinium nordhagenii</i>		H	0.78	FC		
		<i>Ranunculus laetus</i>		H	0.33	FC		
		<i>Ranunculus stewartii</i>		H	0.21	BR		
		<i>Ranunculus trichophyllum</i>		H	0.19	BR		
		<i>Ranunculus arvensis</i>		H	0.04	R		
		35	Polygonaceae	<i>Aconogonum alpinum</i>	Chekroo	H	0.12	BR
				<i>Aconogonum molle</i>	Pan Chola	H	0.02	R
				<i>Rumex hastatus</i>	Hulla	H	2.53	A
				<i>Rumex nepalensis</i>	''	H	1.89	C
				<i>Rheum emodi</i>	Reward	H	0.99	FC
<i>Bistorta affinis</i>	Masloorn			H	2.39	A		
<i>Bistorta amplexicaulis</i>	Masloorn			H	2.32	A		
<i>Bistorta vivipara</i>	Masloorn			H	0.78	FC		
<i>Bistorta emodi</i>	Masloorn			H	1.00	C		
<i>Fagopyrum esculentum</i>	Trumba			H	0.58	FC		
<i>Oxyria digyna</i>	Khatkurla			H	1.98	C		
<i>Persicaria capitata</i>				H	0.05	R		
<i>Polygonum cognatum</i>	Drobra			H	0.18	BR		
<i>Polygonum paronychioides</i>				H	0.68	FC		
<i>Polygonum plebeium</i>				H	1.30	C		

		<i>Rheum australe</i>	Gol Chontal	H	0.07	R
		<i>Rheum webbianum</i>	Chontal	H	0.43	FC
		<i>Rumex acetosa</i>	Hulla	H	0.87	FC
		<i>Rumex nepalensis</i>	Hulla	H	1.23	C
		<i>Rumex patientia</i>	Hulla	H	1.00	C
36	Apiaceae	<i>Aegopodium alpestre</i>	--	H	1.20	C
		<i>Angelica glauca</i>	Chora	H	0.87	FC
		<i>Bupleurum candollei</i>	Kali Boti	H	0.89	FC
		<i>Bupleurum falcatum</i>	Mithi Jiri	H	0.75	FC
		<i>Bupleurum longicaule</i>	Mithi Jiri	H	0.23	BR
		<i>Bupleurum marginatum</i>	Mithi Jiri	H	0.47	FC
		<i>Chaerophyllum capnoides</i>		H	0.66	FC
		<i>Chaerophyllum reflexum</i>		H	0.04	R
		<i>Chaerophyllum villosum</i>		H	0.07	R
		<i>Heraclium candicans</i>	palhar	H	0.45	FC
		<i>Pimpinella acuminata</i>		H	0.87	FC
		<i>Pleurospermum govianum</i>		H	0.97	FC
		<i>Pleurospermum candollei</i>		H	0.34	FC
		<i>Pleurospermum brunonis</i>		H	0.25	BR
		<i>Cortia depressa</i>	Jari	H	0.98	FC
		<i>Selinum tenuifolium</i>		H	0.34	FC
37	Rosaceae	<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>		H	1.23	C
		<i>Agrimonia pilosa</i>		H	0.89	BR
38	Poaceae	<i>Agrostis gigantea</i>	Gagoo	H	1.32	C
		<i>Agrostis stolonifera</i>	Gagoo	H	1.02	C
		<i>Agrostis vernalis</i>	Gha	H	1.89	C
		<i>Agrostis vinealis</i>	Gha	H	1.04	C
		<i>Alopecurus himalaicus</i>	Gha	H	1.78	C
		<i>Apluda dahuricus</i>	Gha	H	0.58	FC
		<i>Apluda mutica</i>	Gha	H	0.99	FC
		<i>Chrysopogon gryllus</i>	Gha	H	1.78	C
		<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	Gha	H	1.26	C
		<i>Eremopoa altaica</i>	Gha	H	2.46	A
		<i>Festuca hartmannii</i>	Gha	H	1.23	C
		<i>Festuca kashmiriana</i>	Gha	H	1.05	C
		<i>Festuca lemarii</i>	Gha	H	0.59	FC
		<i>Elymus dahuricus</i>	Gha	H	0.47	FC
		<i>Helictotrichon virescens</i>	Gha	H	0.26	BR
		<i>Mistegium nodosum</i>	Baroon	H	0.44	FC
		<i>Pennisetum alopecuroides</i>		H	0.89	FC
		<i>Pennisetum flaccidum</i>		H	0.05	R
		<i>Pennisetum lanatum</i>		H	0.18	BR
		<i>Pennisetum annuum</i>		H	0.78	FC
		<i>Phleum alpinum</i>		H	0.69	FC
		<i>Phragmites australis.</i>		H	0.64	FC
		<i>Piptatherum gracile</i>		H	0.54	FC
		<i>Piptatherum laterale</i>		H	0.33	FC
		<i>Poa annua</i>	Gha	H	0.45	FC
		<i>Poa attenuata Trin.</i>		H	0.45	FC
		<i>Poa gracilis Trin.</i>		H	0.36	FC
		<i>Poa nemoralis</i>	Gha	H	2.45	A
		<i>Poa alpina</i>	Bozni Ghaa	H	1.89	C
		<i>Poa angustifolia</i>		H	1.36	C
		<i>Poa baccifera</i>		H	0.46	FC
		<i>Poa pratensis</i>		H	1.36	C
39	Lamiaceae	<i>Ajuga bracteosa</i>	Rattiboti	H	0.36	FC
		<i>Ajuga parviflora</i>	Jan E Adam	H	0.78	FC
		<i>Calamintha umbrosa</i>		H	0.64	FC
		<i>Calanthe tricarinata</i>		H	0.98	FC
		<i>Clinopodium vulgare</i>		H	0.06	R
		<i>Clinopodium piperitum</i>		H	0.78	FC
		<i>Clinopodium umbrosum</i>		H	0.33	FC
		<i>Lamium album</i>		H	0.78	FC
		<i>Leucas cephalotes</i>		H	0.24	R
		<i>Leucas lanata</i>		H	0.34	FC
		<i>Mentha longifolia</i>		H	0.87	FC
		<i>Nepeta elliptica</i>		H	0.36	FC
		<i>Nepeta erecta</i>		H	0.48	FC
		<i>Nepeta laevigata</i>		H	0.45	FC
		<i>Nepeta nervosa.</i>		H	0.69	FC
		<i>Nepeta podostachys</i>		H	0.28	BR
		<i>Origanum vulgare</i>	Bubri Ban	H	0.05	R
		<i>Phlomis bracteosa.</i>		H	0.98	FC
		<i>Phlomis cashmeriana</i>		H	1.36	C
		<i>Phlomis spectabilis</i>		H	0.74	FC
		<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	Thula	H	0.45	FC
		<i>Salvia hians</i>		H	0.78	FC
		<i>Salvia moorcroftiana</i>		H	0.66	FC
		<i>Salvia nubicola</i>		H	0.17	BR
		<i>Thymus linearis</i>	Podina	H	0.09	R
40	Malvaceae	<i>Alcea rosea</i>	Gul E Khair	H	0.48	FC
		<i>Malva parviflora</i>	Sonchal	H	1.65	C
		<i>Malva neglecta</i>	Sonchal	H	1.36	C
41	Rosaceae	<i>Alchemilla trollii</i>		H	1.00	C
		<i>Filipendula ulmaria</i>	Kasi Patra	H	1.36	C
		<i>Fragaria nubicola</i>	Khan Merchan	H	0.89	FC
		<i>Potentilla anserina</i>		H	0.46	FC

		<i>Potentilla atrosanguinea</i>	Mali Chae	H	0.89	FC
		<i>Potentilla cathaclinis</i>	Mali Chae	H	0.45	FC
		<i>Potentilla curviseta</i>	Mali Chae	H	0.36	FC
		<i>Potentilla monanthes</i>	Mali Chae	H	0.87	FC
		<i>Potentilla nepalensis</i>	Mali Chae	H	0.44	FC
		<i>Potentilla ochreatea</i>	Mali Chae	H	0.76	FC
		<i>Sibbaldia cuneata</i>		H	0.14	BR
		<i>Sibbaldia purpurea</i>		H	0.07	R
		<i>Sibbaldia tetrandra</i>		H	1.45	C
		<i>Sorbaria tomentosa</i>		H	1.3	C
		<i>Sorbus lanata</i>		H	0.46	FC
42	Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium carolinianum</i>	Pyaz	H	1.43	C
		<i>Allium humile</i>	Pyaz	H	1.08	C
		<i>Allium tuberosum</i>	Mali Ka Pyaz	H	1.63	C
		<i>Allium wallichii</i>	Mali Ka Payaz	H	0.99	FC
43	Primulaceae	<i>Anagallis arvensis</i>		H	0.44	FC
		<i>Androsace longifolia</i>		H	0.99	FC
		<i>Androsace primuloides</i>		H	0.74	FC
		<i>Androsace rotundifolia</i>		H	0.63	FC
		<i>Androsace sempervivoides</i>		H	0.09	R
		<i>Anglica cyclocarpa</i>	Murchar	H	0.78	FC
		<i>Cortusa brotheri</i>		H	0.36	FC
		<i>Primula denticulata</i>	Mameera	H	0.79	FC
		<i>Primula edgeworthii</i>	Mameera	H	0.99	FC
		<i>Primula elliptica</i>	Mameera	H	0.78	FC
		<i>Primula macrophyla</i>	Mameera	H	0.68	FC
		<i>Primula reptans</i>	Mameera	H	0.64	FC
		<i>Primula rosea</i>	Mameera	H	1.2	C
		<i>Primula stuartii</i>	Mameera	H	0.65	FC
44	Brassicaceae	<i>Arabis amplexicaulis</i>		H	0.36	FC
		<i>Draba cachemirica.</i>		H	0.94	FC
		<i>Draba oreades</i>		H	0.93	FC
		<i>Rorippa montana</i>		H	0.90	FC
		<i>Thlaspi kotschyannum</i>	Mali Da Sag	H	0.39	FC
		<i>Thlaspi perfoliatum</i>	Mali Da Sag	H	0.46	FC
45	Araceae	<i>Arisaema nepanthoides</i>	Sur Ganda	H	0.33	FC
		<i>Arisaema flavum Schott</i>	Sur Ganda	H	0.24	BR
		<i>Arisaema intermedium</i>	Sur Ganda	H	0.43	FC
		<i>Arisaema tortosum</i>	Sur Ganda	H	0.53	FC
46	Boraginaceae	<i>Arnebia benthamii</i>	Gaw Zaban	H	1.20	C
		<i>Arnebia euchroma</i>	Gaw Zaban	H	0.36	FC
		<i>Cynoglossum zeylanicum</i>	Mali Ka Cheroo	H	1.23	C
		<i>Cynoglossum lanceolatum</i>	Mali Ka Cheroo	H	0.56	FC
		<i>Lindelofia longiflora</i>	Lhndi	H	0.45	FC
		<i>Lindelofia longiflora</i>	Lhndi	H	0.98	FC
		<i>Lindelofia stylosa</i>		H	0.34	FC
		<i>Lindelofia macrostyla</i>		H	0.46	FC
		<i>Pseudomertensia echioides</i>	Cheero	H	0.99	FC
		<i>Pseudomertensia molikioides</i>	Cheero	H	0.45	FC
		<i>Pseudomertensia molikioides</i>	Lhndi	H	0.58	FC
		<i>Pseudomertensia nemorosa</i>	Lhndi	H	0.36	FC
47	Liliaceae	<i>Asparagus adscendens</i>	Chae	H	0.46	FC
		<i>Fritillaria roylei</i>	Jangli Thom	H	1.33	C
		<i>Lilium polyphyllum</i>		H	0.12	BR
		<i>Polygonatum multiflorum</i>	Kawar Gandal	H	0.66	FC
		<i>Polygonatum verticillatum</i>	Kawar Gandal	H	0.98	FC
48	Fabaceae	<i>Astragalus candolleanus</i>	Miswak	H	1.23	C
		<i>Astragalus frigidus</i>	Miswak	H	0.78	FC
		<i>Astragalus himalayanus</i>	Miswak	H	0.78	FC
		<i>Astragalus subumbellatus</i>	Miswak	H	0.76	FC
		<i>Astragalus grahamianus</i>		H	0.34	FC
		<i>Astragalus oplites</i>		H	0.69	FC
		<i>Astragalus rhizanthus</i>		H	0.78	FC
		<i>Hadsarum cacHirianum</i>		H	0.63	FC
		<i>Indigofera haterantha</i>	Kanthee	H	0.48	FC
		<i>Indigofera himalayensis</i>	Kanthee	H	0.36	FC
		<i>Lathyrus laevigatus</i>	Bun Phali	H	0.74	FC
		<i>Lathyrus pratensis</i>	Bun Phali	H	0.36	FC
		<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>		H	0.46	FC
		<i>Oxytropis lapponica</i>		H	0.96	FC
		<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Shatal	H	0.98	FC
		<i>Trifolium repens</i>	Shatal	H	0.78	FC
		<i>Trigonella emodi</i>	Methi	H	0.99	FC
		<i>Trigonella falcata</i>	Methi	H	0.78	FC
		<i>Vicia narbonensis.</i>	Matri	H	0.36	FC
49	Solanaceae	<i>Atropa acuminata</i>	Lubar	H	0.36	FC
		<i>Atropa belladonna</i>	Challa lubbar	H	0.22	BR
		<i>Hyoscyamus niger</i>		H	0.98	FC
		<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	Kach mach	H	1.20	C
		<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>	Mirchola	H	1.00	C
50	Acanthaceae	<i>Barleria cristata</i>		H	1.48	C
51	Saxifragaceae	<i>Bergenia ciliata</i>	Bat Bhewa	H	1.66	C
		<i>Bergenia purpurascens</i>	Bat Bhewa	H	1.53	C
		<i>Bergenia strachevi</i>	Bat Bhewa	H	1.74	C
		<i>Saxifraga flagellaris</i>		H	0.94	FC
		<i>Saxifraga jacquemontiana</i>		H	0.46	FC
		<i>Saxifraga parmassifolia</i>		H	0.43	FC

		<i>Saxifraga stenophylla</i>		H	0.63	FC
		<i>Saxifraga strigosa</i>		H	0.78	FC
52	Cyperaceae	<i>Blasmus compressus</i>		H	0.69	FC
		<i>Carex atrofusca</i>		H	0.41	FC
		<i>Carex buxbaumii</i>		H	0.89	FC
		<i>Carex cardiolepis</i>		H	0.02	R
		<i>Carex psychrophila</i>		H	0.97	FC
53	Campanulaceae	<i>Campanula aristata</i>		H	0.36	FC
		<i>Campanula cashmeriana</i>		H	0.48	FC
		<i>Campanula latifolia</i>		H	0.48	FC
		<i>Codonopsis clematidea</i>		H	0.19	BR
		<i>Codonopsis ovata</i>		H	0.48	FC
		<i>Codonopsis viridis</i>	Phakli Boti	H	0.48	FC
54	Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>		H	0.32	FC
		<i>Cardamine hirsuta</i>		H	0.19	BR
		<i>Cardamine loxostemonides</i>		H	0.43	FC
		<i>Cardamine macrophylla</i>		H	0.89	FC
55	Ericaceae	<i>Cassiope festigiata</i>		H	0.34	FC
56	Chenopodiaceae	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	Bathwa	H	1.43	C
		<i>Chenopodium phylloglossum</i>	Bathwa	H	1.36	C
		<i>Chenopodium foliosum</i>	Bathwa	H	1.45	C
57	Onagraceae	<i>Circaea alpina</i>		H	1.36	C
		<i>Epilobium angustifolium</i>		H	0.69	FC
		<i>Epilobium laxum</i>		H	0.14	BR
		<i>Epilobium parviflorum</i>		H	0.09	R
		<i>Epilobium royleanum</i>		H	0.04	R
		<i>Epilobium wallichianum</i>		H	0.43	FC
		<i>Oenothera rosea</i>		H	0.96	FC
58	Papaveraceae	<i>Corydalis govaniana</i>		H	0.48	FC
		<i>Corydalis stewartii</i>		H	0.44	FC
		<i>Meconopsis aculeata</i>		H	0.12	
59	Convolvulaceae	<i>Cuscuta europaea</i>	Neela Dhari	H	0.99	FC
		<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i>	Neela Dhari	H	0.89	FC
60	Orchidaceae	<i>Dactylorhiza hatagirea</i>	Nar Mada	H	1.00	C
		<i>Habenaria pectinata</i>		H	0.36	FC
61	Caryophyllaceae	<i>Dianthus anatolicus</i>		H	0.41	FC
62	Dioscoraceae	<i>Dioscorea deltoidea</i>		H	0.99	FC
63	Dipsacaceae	<i>Dipsacus inermis</i>	Opulha	H	0.49	FC
		<i>Monira coulteriana</i>		H	0.35	FC
		<i>Morina longifolia</i>	Mali Kanda	H	1.62	C
64	Lamiaceae	<i>Dracocephalum</i>		H	0.42	FC
65	Equisetaceae	<i>Equisetum</i>		H	0.78	FC
		<i>Equisetum debile</i>		H	0.87	FC
66	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Dohdal	H	1.36	C
		<i>Euphorbia wallichii</i>	Hervi	H	1.63	C
		<i>Euphorbia strachevi</i>	Dohdal	H	1.11	C
67	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Euphrasia himalayica</i>		H	0.04	R
		<i>Lagotis cashmeriana</i>	Kali Hind	H	0.63	FC
		<i>Pedicularis bicornuta</i>		H	0.45	FC
		<i>Pedicularis oederi</i>		H	0.24	BR
		<i>Pedicularis pectinata</i>		H	0.65	FC
		<i>Pedicularis punctata</i>		H	0.06	R
		<i>Pedicularis pyramidata</i>		H	0.36	FC
		<i>Pedicularis scullyana</i>		H	0.03	R
		<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>		H	0.14	BR
		<i>Veronica himalensis</i>		H	0.89	FC
		<i>Veronica polita</i>		H	0.33	FC
		<i>Veronica alpina</i>		H	0.78	FC
72	Gentianaceae	<i>Exacum tetragonum</i>		H	0.41	FC
		<i>Gentiana carinata</i>		H	0.98	FC
		<i>Gentiana depressa</i>		H	0.34	FC
		<i>Gentiana kurroo</i>		H	0.14	BR
		<i>Gentiana phylocalyx</i>		H	0.14	BR
		<i>Gentianodes alii</i>		H	0.98	FC
		<i>Jaeschkea oligosperma</i>		H	0.75	FC
		<i>Sewertia cuneata</i>	Rech Endeh	H	1.99	C
		<i>Swertia petiolata</i>	Rech Endeh	H	1.78	C
		<i>Swertia speciosa</i>	Rech Endeh	H	1.69	C
68	Rubiaceae	<i>Galium asperuloides</i>	Bhangri	H	1.89	C
		<i>Galium boreale</i>		H	2.02	A
		<i>Galium verum</i>		H	0.95	FC
		<i>Galium aparine</i>		H	0.36	FC
69	Geraniaceae	<i>Geranium himalayense</i>	Ratan Jot	H	0.64	FC
		<i>Geranium nepalense</i>	Ratan Jot	H	0.14	BR
		<i>Geranium pratense</i>	Ratan Jot	H	2.25	A
		<i>Geranium wallichianum</i>	Ratan Jot	H	1.36	C
70	Caryophyllaceae	<i>Gypsophila cerastioides</i>		H	0.34	FC
		<i>Gypsophila oreades</i>		H	0.94	FC
71	Boraginaceae	<i>Hackelia uncinata</i>		H	0.23	BR
72	Hypericaceae	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	Pelly Dudh Jari	H	0.46	FC
73	Hypoxidaceae	<i>Hypoxis aurea</i>		H	0.98	FC
74	Balsaminaceae	<i>Impatiens brachycentra</i>	Buntil	H	1.30	C
		<i>Impatiens edgeworthii</i>	Buntil	H	1.98	C
		<i>Impatiens grandulifera</i>	Buntil	H	1.56	C
		<i>Impatiens thomsonii</i>	Buntil	H	1.00	C
		<i>Impatiens bicolor</i>	Buntil	H	1.75	C
75	Iridaceae	<i>Iris decora</i>	Ghori Ghaa	H	1.36	C

		<i>Iris hookariana</i>	Ghori Ghaa	H	1.99	C
		<i>Iris kashmiriana</i>	Ghori Ghaa	H	2.36	A
		<i>Iris lactea</i>	Ghori Ghaa	H	1.45	C
76	Juncaceae	<i>Juncus articulatus</i>		H	0.36	FC
		<i>Juncus himalensis</i>		H	0.46	FC
		<i>Juncus membranaceus</i>		H	2.34	A
		<i>Juncus thomsonii</i>		H	0.64	FC
77	Ranunculaceae	<i>Lavatera kashmiriana</i>	Thandi Booti	H	0.47	FC
		<i>Ranunculus hirtellus</i>		H	0.94	FC
		<i>Ranunculus hirtellus</i>		H	0.47	FC
		<i>Ranunculus stewartii</i>		H	0.36	FC
		<i>Ranunculus trichophyllus</i>		H	0.64	FC
		<i>Ranunculus arvensis</i>		H	0.78	FC
		<i>Trolium acaulis</i>		H	0.36	FC
78	Caryophyllaceae	<i>Minuartia kashmirica</i>		H	0.48	FC
		<i>Minuartia uniflora</i>	Bat Karam	H	0.36	FC
		<i>Silene edgeworthii</i>	Murkanar	H	0.87	FC
		<i>Silene gonosperma</i>	Murkanar	H	0.14	BR
		<i>Silene viscosa</i>	Murkanar	H	0.99	FC
		<i>Silene vulgaris</i>	Murkanar	H	0.88	FC
		<i>Stellaria decumbens</i>		H	0.34	FC
		<i>Stellaria media</i>		H	0.96	FC
		<i>Stellaria nemorum</i>		H	0.34	FC
79	Tamaricaceae	<i>Myricaria elegans</i>		H	1.25	C
80	Orobanchaceae	<i>Orobanche alba</i>		H	0.36	FC
81	Oxalidaceae	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	Khatla	H	0.04	R
82	Parnassiaceae	<i>Parnassia nubicola</i>		H	0.14	BR
83	Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>		H	0.06	R
		<i>Plantago major</i>		H	1.36	C
		<i>Plantago alpina</i>		H	1.00	C
		<i>Plantago depressa</i>		H	1.04	C
84	Polemoniaceae	<i>Polemonium caeruleum</i>		H	0.78	FC
85	Polygalaceae	<i>Polygala sibirica</i>		H	1.36	FC
		<i>Polygonum alpinum</i>		H	3.65	A
		<i>Polygonum amplexicaule</i>		H	2.36	A
		<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>		H	0.15	BR
		<i>Rheum tibeticum</i>		H	1.87	C
86	Crassulaceae	<i>Rhodiola heterodonta</i>	Bug Masti	H	1.33	C
		<i>Rhodiola himalayensis</i>	Sabr Jari	H	1.36	C
		<i>Rhodiola fastigiata</i>	Bug Masti	H	0.35	FC
		<i>Rosularia adenotricha</i>		H	0.64	FC
		<i>Sedum eversii</i>		H	0.34	FC
		<i>Sedum oreades</i>		H	0.46	FC
		<i>Sedum trullipetalum</i>		H	0.64	FC
87	Zingiberaceae	<i>Roscoea alpina</i>		H	1.47	C
88	Podophyllaceae	<i>Sinopodophyllum</i>	Kakari	H	1.89	C
89	Urticaceae	<i>Urtica hyperborea</i>	Kerii	H	1.36	C
90	Valerianaceae	<i>Valeriana jatamansi</i>	Mushki Baala	H	1.03	C
		<i>Valeriana pyrolifolia</i>	Manj Jari	H	0.36	FC
		<i>Valeriana wallichii</i>		H	0.04	R
91	Apocynaceae	<i>Vincetoxicum arnottianum</i>	Phal Wala Poda	H	0.36	FC
92	Violaceae	<i>Viola biflora</i>	Banfsha	H	1.36	C
		<i>Viola canescens</i>	Banfsha	H	0.88	FC
		<i>Viola kashmiriana</i>	Banfsha	H	0.74	FC
		<i>Viola pyrolifolia</i>		H	0.36	FC

Table 2: Recorded communities, localities, elevation, number of species their diversity indices in study area during 2020-21.

Sr#	Communities	localities	Alt. (m)	Coordinates		No of Sp.	Shannon	Simpson	Evenness	Richness	Maturity index
				N	E						
1	C1-Pinus - Indigofera-Viburnum	Ghamot Village	2482	34°56'30.55	74°13'01.87	72	4.14	0.981	0.88	1.52	82.9
2	C2 -Abies-Viburnum-Juniperus-	Saral	2535	34°56'28.98	74°12'54.01	75	4.11	0.977	0.81	1.60	76.0
3	C3-Abies-Acer- Berberis	Alif Rakh	2722	34°57'06.64	74°13'17.57	75	4.23	0.984	0.91	1.62	68.9
4	C4-Pinus-Viburnum-Lonicera	Kundi Village	2592	34°57'31.95	74°13'44.75	76	4.25	0.984	0.92	1.73	60.5
5	C5-Rosa-Abies-Betula	Samgam Malii	2944	34°54'49.82	74°12'13.36	62	4.05	0.981	0.93	1.61	56.7
6	C6-Salix-Myricaria-Viburnum	Near Alihol Bhaik	3017	34°59'50.29	74°14'11.19	61	4.04	0.981	0.93	1.63	57.6
7	C7-Robus-Polygonum-Artemisia	Kamakhodari Nar	3377	35°00'11.83	74°13'01.22	93	4.42	0.986	0.89	1.87	57.3
8	C8-Betula-Juniperus-Lonicera-	Ratta Chang	3615	34°58'34.96	74°13'14.24	54	3.90	0.978	0.91	1.47	60.6
9	C9-Juniperus-Salix-Aconitum	Saral Nar	3219	35°00'00.91	74°08'59.71	74	4.21	0.983	0.91	1.73	64.2
10	C10-Rosa-Gaultheria-Aconitum	Kothalii	3487	35°01'24.72	74°08'00.92	99	4.53	0.989	0.94	1.92	62.6
11	C11-Juniperus-Rhododendron-Sibbaldia	Habib Bhaik Top	3871	34°11'16.99	74°13'14.24	60	3.92	0.974	0.84	1.43	63.1
12	C12-Bistorta-Aconitum-Pedicularis	Saral Bhaik	3499	35°01'29.00	74°07'47.48	71	4.16	0.983	0.90	1.64	60.8
13	C13-Sibbaldia-Bistorta-Lagotis	Ghol Basti Top	3998	34°59'35.52	74°04'38.24	23	3.07	0.951	0.94	0.86	75.1
14	C14-Bistorta-Anaphalis -Potentilla	Kamakhodri lake	4060	35°04'21.47	74°10'40.88	55	3.95	0.979	0.94	1.29	69.8
15	C15-Poa-Anaphalis-Geum	Saral Lake	4212	34°03'05.74	74°08'55.70	31	3.37	0.963	0.94	0.90	66.0
16	C16-Rhododendron-Bistorta-Corydalis	Rata Chang Top	4062	34°58'10.39	74°12'08.13	63	4.08	0.982	0.94	1.38	62.7
17	C17-Anaphalis-Rheum-Poa	Jor Di Gali	4174	34°59'21.20	74°03'43.86	49	3.86	0.978	0.97	1.07	71.1
18	C18-Allium-Cassiope-Bistorta	Top of Alihol Bhaik	3972	35°00'27.65	74°14'26.40	41	3.68	0.974	0.97	0.99	79.8